

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PIANO PERFORMANCE IN MUSICAL CULTURE

Gadelshina Nailya Anvarovna

Music teacher of the Military Music Academic Lyceum of the
National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan
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Abstract: This article provides scientific-theoretical instructions on forming the performance skills of students-young people on the piano. There were also opinions about the importance of the piano in musical culture.

Key words: students, piano, musical instrument, skill, educational system, methodology.

"People of culture and art are active,
should live with new creative ideas and initiatives"

Sh. Mirziyoyev.

Under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, on March 19, 2020, it was planned to increase attention to youth, to widely involve the young generation in culture, art, physical education and sports, and to use information technologies in them correctly. A meeting was held on the issues of formation of culture, promotion of reading among young people, provision of women's employment. As it is known, the head of our state put forward five important initiatives to start work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres on the basis of a new system. The very first initiative serves to increase the interest of young people in music, painting, literature, theater and other types of art, and to reveal their talent. Today, there are more than 800 cultural centers, 312 music and art schools, and 130,000 boys and girls are enrolled. It was noted that it was not installed. At the same time, helping creative people and supporting their talent is one of the urgent tasks of each of us today.

In ensuring the maturity of any society, the importance of the art of music and the performance of musical instruments, which are considered the wealth of the purity and spiritual world of the human race, is great. A wide path has been opened for the restoration of our national values. Islam Abdug'anievich Karimov, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, wrote in his work "High Spirituality is an Invincible Power" that "musical sounds express the most noble, high and delicate human experiences, no matter what people or nations perform them." Therefore, the role and importance of our national musical works in Uzbek music, the stages of development are still significant.

Uzbek piano music spans a quarter of a century. But in a very short period of time, he went through a fantastic process of development and managed to create mature Uzbek models that correspond to the great monumental piano works of

Europe. To date, a number of new works in the field of music are brought to the attention of our people. Our young people are making unprecedented progress in this regard.

Piano playing is one of the most popular types of music. Everyone knows that every nation has its own national musical instruments. Today, there are also the most popular universal musical instruments among all the peoples of the world. One of them is the piano. Among all the world's famous composers, Uzbek composers also created brilliant works for this instrument. They are lovingly performed by young performers.

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One of the important sections of the educational work conducted in the piano class is the cultural-educational activity of the students. One of the forms of educational work is the discussion of a student concert. In this case, the student will have a critical view of performance, and a certain level of preparation for independent teaching activities will begin. The indicator level of the learning process on the piano course is mainly related to the organizational aspects of the lesson. Conducting educational work determines the content, form, and style of the educational process. The level of students' mastery is mainly related to the goal-oriented structure of the curriculum. It should specify specific pedagogical tasks: individual aspects of the student, level of preparation, sequence of learning musical material, etc. The performance repertoire should include Uzbek and classical works, as well as artistically high works of different forms, content, and styles by foreign composers.

When talking about the musical instruments of the present time, one of the widely used musical instruments is the piano, which is used equally in the West and the East. It is probably interesting for music listeners who are not experts in this field to know the information about how the piano instrument appeared.

Fortepiano means hard-slow, a musical instrument with strings, invented and made by Cristofori Bartalameo (1709-1711) in Italy.

In fact, the history of this musical instrument goes back to very ancient times, that is, to ancient Greece. At the time of Pythagoras, the founder of the theory of multiplication, there was a musical instrument known as a monochord. It consisted of a long thin box that was pulled narrowly over the instrument. Since this box is made of special wood, the sound coming out of it is loud and has its own timbre. The string was fastened to the box with a non-movable harrak, besides which there was another movable harrak, which was moved on the string and served to lower or raise the musical sound. Over time, other strings were added to one string. This instrument is played with a special nohun (mediator), and sometimes by hitting the strings with a special stick or hammer. Over the centuries, this instrument has been improved. The box becomes larger and becomes rectangular, and the keyboard is placed on one side. Now the musician started to play by pressing the key, the metal plates that were adapted to it created the sound by scratching the strings. This instrument was called clavichord. It is performed standing on the table. The clavichord instrument appeared in the 12th century, and masters living in several countries tried to improve it for five centuries. Several strings were added to each key and the size of the box was increased to make the music sounds strong and solid. Over time, several keyboards were added to the clavichord, each keyboard instrument served to expand and amplify the sound range. Even these actions could not serve to increase the sound of the musical instrument. Because the clavichord was made of precious wood, it served to decorate the hotels of rich people.

At the end of the 17th century, in France, the lower white keyboards were made of black wood, and the upper ones were made of ivory. The reason it was made in this way was that in those days, more women - girls played keyboard instruments, and to enjoy the attractive hand movements of ladies playing clavichords with white hands on black keyboards. But the intermediate lines between such black keyboards were mixed, invisible and difficult for the player. By the 18th century, keyboards began to be arranged in the same way as on the piano today.

At the same time as the clavichord, another keyboard instrument similar to it began to develop, and it was called by different names: clavicimbal, harpsichord, virginal, harpsichord. The last one became so widespread that other similar instruments of various forms were called by one common name.

By the 19th century, there were mainly two types of piano instruments: a horizontal piano and a vertical piano. A grand piano is used in large concert halls to sound a full-scale powerful musical tone in a concert, while a piano is used in rooms that can be heard slowly and empty.

Currently, this instrument is used in musical culture classes of general education schools, in the teaching of all folk instruments in music and art schools, in art and culture colleges, in music courses of higher educational institutions, tools are widely used.

References:

1. Borukhzon, Im, Volchek, Il, Guseynova, Ilm alphabet of musical fantasy. Moscow: Music, 1995.
2. Limanskaya, E. P. young composer. - Samara, 1995. — 37 pages.
3. Macligin, A. L. Improvisation on the piano. Moscow 2006.
4. Turgeneva, E. Organization of the educational process in small piano classes. — Moscow: Music, 1990.
5. Shatkovsky, "Development of musical hearing." — Moscow: Music, 1996.

